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ABSTRACT

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CONSERVATION OF WORLD WAR II AIRCRAFT HERITAGE: AN ASSESSMENT OF INNOVATIVE PROTECTIVE COATINGS THROUGH ACCELERATED AGEING TESTS

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1. Introduction

The PROCRAFT European project aims at developing conservation procedures for historical aircraft. In this framework, 3-mercapto-propyl-trimethoxysilane (PropS-SH) and Cutin coatings were tested as green alternatives to Paraloid B72 (PB72).

Two historical Al alloy (ca. 4 Cu, 0.6 Mg, 0.2 Si, wt.%) components were sampled: (i) One rolled fuselage plate retaining original paint with Zn and Ti pigments, and (ii) a wrought propeller blade with marine corrosion. Coupons from each one were investigated in uncoated, PB72-coated (benchmark), Cutin- or PropS-SH-coated conditions.

After documentation, the samples were artificially aged for a 20 days total under runoff conditions with synthetic acid rain (AR), to be followed by 14 days of climatic chamber ageing in the dark and under UV-A. Documentation included weighting, profilometry, colorimetry, professional photography, 3-D digital microscopy, scanning electron microscopy coupled with energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM-EDS), attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) and Raman spectroscopies.

AR was analyzed by atomic emission spectroscopy (MP-AES) to measure metal release (Al for corroded and Zn for painted samples).

2. Results and Discussion

As regards metal release from corroded samples of the propeller blade, PB72 coating seems to lower the release of Al by almost an order of magnitude in respect to uncoated samples. Measuring Zn release from the painted samples proved less diagnostic, as Zn release from unprotected painted samples decreased and disappeared after the first dripping phases due to fast depletion by leaching.

Therefore, more attention was given to surface modifications in terms of chemical, topographic and mass changes. SEM-EDS proved particularly diagnostic: Unprotected corroded samples showed an increase in Al and Cu concentration, and a decrease in Ca, pointing to concretion dissolution. When these samples were protected with PB72, in addition to the C and O signals coming from the coating, low signals of Ca and Si from surface concretions were detected, as well as low Al signals coming from the substrate.

For unprotected painted samples, ageing led to an increase in Ti and Fe contribution on the surface, and a decrease in Zn (due to the higher solubility of Zn pigments). Instead, after ageing PB72-coated painted samples, the initial C and O signals coming from PB72 were modified by a higher contribution of Zn followed by Ti and S, pointing to the higher solubility of Zn compounds, and revealed the apparition of bubbling defects in the PB72 coating.

The aesthetic impact of the color change caused by coating and ageing was assessed by colorimetry and by processing professional registry images in ImageJ, considering only color changes above the relative standard deviation. For the corroded and painted uncoated samples, ageing caused a total color variation (ΔE) between 3 and 3.5.

Regarding PB72, coating created no significant difference in corroded and painted samples, as neither did PropS-SH coating on painted samples ($\Delta E < 1.7$). Even after ageing, these samples showed negligible color variations ($\Delta E < 3$).

Cutin application caused yellowing for both corroded and painted samples. Such color changes might be due to carotenoid impurities from the tomato source material for Cutin production. However, after ageing, samples coated with Cutin showed color variation always well within the acceptable threshold ($\Delta E \leq 5$), especially for painted samples.

Runoff ageing and testing is underway for samples coated with Cutin and PropS-SH, together with climatic chamber ageing of all samples. Metal release, SEM-EDS, color and mass variation evaluations, will allow to better understand the advantages and limitations of each protective coating.

3. Conclusions

Thus far, PropS-SH seems a good alternative to Paraloid B72. Cutin, due to its yellowish color contribution, does not seem recommendable yet for cultural heritage protection applications on white/silver metallic surfaces. Future improvements for the production of less-colored cutin polymer could solve this issue and enable its use as a naturally-sourced, non-hazardous alternative for heritage aluminium substrates, particularly when dark, heterogenous or exposed under irregular illumination conditions.

Accelerated ageing scheme

Fig 1. Artificial ageing scheme

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